

BALALAR FOLKLOR SAZ ÁSPABLARÍ HÁM ATAMALARÍ HAQQÍDA

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Annotaciya. Bul maqalada balalar folklor saz áspablari hám atamaları haqqında sóz etilgen.

Gilt sózi: Folklor, balalar, saz áspab, muzıka, qobız, qosıq, shıǵarma, qobız atamaları.

ABOUT CHILDREN'S FOLKLORE INSTRUMENTS AND NAMES

Abstract. This article tells about children's folklore instruments and their names.

Key word: folklore, children, the word áspab, music, kobyz, spoon, artwork, kobyz names.

О ДЕТСКИХ ФОЛЬКЛОРНЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТАХ И НАЗВАНИЯХ

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о детских фольклорных инструментах и их названиях.

Ключевое слово: фольклор, дети, слово áspab, музыка, кобыз, ложка, произведение искусства, имена кобыз.

Áyyemgi zamanlarda “qobız” uǵımı ulıwma “saz ásbabı” maǵanasın ańlatsa kerek. Sebebi, balalarǵa arnalǵan sazqobız sırnaydıń qızıl ılaydan islengen túri de, al jelqobız mes tárızles ásbap ekeni belgili. Saraylarda saqlanǵan narqobız (qobız – bas) benen qarapayım balaqobız (qobız – prima) ulıwma túsinikten qobız (qızılqobız) atalmısh sazdıń biri úlkeni, ekinshisi kishi túri bolsa, skripkaǵa megzes sımqobız tarlı ásbap túrine kiredi. Birazlar onı “ıyıq” (“ıyinqobız”) dese, qazaq halqı “sazgen” dep ataydı. Qádimgi kábıqobız (qobızqabaq) qabaqtan islense, shıńqobız (Buxara qaraqalpaqlarında “shańǵıawız” – S. A.) temirden jasaladı. Qırǵızlarda ol “temirqobız” degen atamaǵa iye. Qullası, bári de saz ásbabınıń túrleri. Balalardıń birewi bir gáp aytıp turıp, onı ekinshisi basqasha uqsa, ádepki balanıń “Men ne dedim, qobızım ne deydi...” dep teńlesiniń ańsız atawlısına baylanıslı kelip shıqqan bolsa, ájep emes.

Jámlep kelgende, balalar folklorınıń ózinde kóplegen saz ásbaplarınıń atları ataladı, ayırımlarınıń kelip shıǵıwı haqqında ájayıp ápsanalar dóretilgen. Usı saz ásbaplarınıń tariyxın úyreniw menen qatar, olarǵa baylanıslı awızeki dóretpelerdi jıynap, qayta tiklew máselesi,

balalardıń ruwxıy dúnyasın ǵana emes, qaraqalpaq xalqınıń muzıkalıq folklor keńisligin de keńeyte túsetuǵınlıǵı tábiyiy. Hár bir folklorlıq shıǵarmaları hár túrli dáwirlerdi basınan keshirip, ózine tán bolǵan mazmun hám kórkemlilik ózgesheligin toplaı, áwladan – áwladqa ótip kelgen. Sonlıqtan hár bir folklorlıq shıǵarmalar tariyxıy tamırına, dóreliw sebeplerine iye boladı. Qaraqalpaq xalqıda óziniń barlıq turmısınıń quwanışın, qapashılıǵın folklorlıq shıǵarmalar arqalı bayanlap toy – tamasha, qayǵı - muńın atqaratuǵın bay folklorlıq shıǵarmaların dóretken.

Bul balalar folklorlıq qosıqları qaraqalpaq folklorınıń ishinde ulken orındı iyeleydi.

Xalqımız onı ásirler boyına atadan - balaǵa miyras etip qaldırıp, búgingi kunge shekem jetip kelgen. Bul balalar folklorlıq shıǵarmaları awızdan – awızǵa kóship, óz boyına salıstırıw, teńew qusaǵan kóp ǵana kórkemlew quralların jámlegen. Sonlıqtan ol kóbinese aytıwǵa qolay, tili jeńil tez yadda qalatuǵın, tásirsheń tayın qatarlar bolıp keledi. Sonıń menen birge balalar folklorlıq qosıqlarınıń qaysı túrin alıp qarasańda tereń tárbiyalıq mazmunǵa iye boladı. Bul qosıqlardıń hár bir qatarı balalarǵa tárbiyalıq tásir jasap otıradı.

Bul folklorlıq shıǵarmalar qaysı dáwirde bolsa da balalar turmısına tásir jasap kelip, olardıń ruwxıy dúnyasına málim bir dárejede juwap bererlik bolıp keledi. Juwmaqlap aytqanda balalar folklorlıq shıǵarmaları xalıq penen birge jasap, onıń ómir turmıslıq tariyxıynıń belgilerin kórsetetuǵın janr bolıp esaplanadı.

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Man'lay shertpek

S. Palwanov muzikası.

Moderato

5
Ke - wil - de - gi ko'z be - nen ser - lep, ser - lep qa - ran' - lar

9
sez gir - bol - san' se - zip al, kim shert - ke - nin, ya - ran - lar.

13
1. 2.

17
Man' lay shert - pek de - gen - de

T.S.M.

2

21

man'-lay shert-pek, ya-ran - lar.

25

sez - gir bol - san' se - zip al kim shert - ke - nin, ya - ran - lar.

29

Hey Hey.

Kewildegı kóz benen serlep serlep qarańlar,
Sezgır bolsań sezıp al, kim shertkenin yaranlar.
Mańlay shertpek degende, mańlay shertpek yaranlar.
Sezgır bolsań, sezıp al kim shertkenin yaranlar,

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